

DESIGNER LINEAR VISCOELASTIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS TAILORED TO OPTIMIZE ENERGY HARVESTING

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ABSTRACT

Motion damping by energy harvesting through piezoelectric devices recharging batteries and having it available to do useful work rather than simply dissipating energy by heat is a preferable process. The piezo devices then potentially acquire triple functions as sensors, controllers and/or harvesters. While the piezoelectric devices may not necessarily completely damp out unstable motions, they may contain them by postponing the inevitable instabilities to occur at later times, higher velocities and/or loads, etc. (creep buckling, torsional divergence, flutter, failure conditions, etc.).

The inverse calculus of variation analysis developed in [1] is applied to the current formulation in order to determine among others optimum fiber orientations, number of plies, material properties, piezo device placements, weight, cost, etc. These answers are achieved through solutions of the governing relations and optimum parameter values are obtained subject to enumerated constraints. One of the most fruitful approaches for these goals is to employ Lagrange multipliers.

The analytical formulation is predicated on distinct linear viscoelastic material properties for the composite and for the piezoelectric devices. Furthermore, provisions are incorporated for the spatial distributions of such properties to be represented by distinct optimized functions thus leading to viscoelastic functionally graded composites and piezoelectric devices – both as nonhomogeneous materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

The advent of flexible flight vehicles of any size necessitates analyses based on aeroelastic considerations. In the case of high polymer matrix composites viscoelastic material characterizations must be used instead of elastic ones. In particular, in highly flexible UAVs and MAVs the use of piezoelectric (PZT) devices can be used to extract energy to charge the already present batteries. In that sense is not only energy harvesting a possibility but feedback can also be achieved to improve torsional divergence, flutter, control effectiveness, etc., velocities. This can be effected through the use of optimal designer structural and PZT materials [1], [2]. Fig. 1 illustrates the energy flow and its function and consequences.

While this illustration appears to clearly delineate the two functions in reality they are interrelated and constitute a closed loop system in themselves. The PZT devices exercise control, whether intended or not, through energy dissipation or harvesting or both and vice versa. In other words care must be applied to not introduce detrimental controls while harvesting energy and/or apply controls which significantly reduce the energy that can be extracted and stored.

In cases of open loop dynamical systems one is concerned about natural frequencies and displacement amplitudes and the relations between mass and stiffness is well defined. In closed loop systems, particularly where instability (buckling, torsional divergence, flutter, control reversal, etc.) is of major concern, the interactions between inertia, stiffness, damping, aerodynamics, servo-controls and PZT devices are not analytically readily defined and must be examined on a case by case basis. Here the major players are the phase relations, angle of attack and flight velocity among these six factors.

Consequently, extreme care must be exercised when harvesting energy so as to not disturb equilibrium conditions and avoid torsional divergence, flutter, control loss, etc., instabilities. Furthermore, fail-safe scenarios must be developed for alternate conditions of zero energy harvesting due to either possible piezoelectric equipment malfunctions or fully charged batteries.

The theoretical aspects of linear viscoelasticity are well established as evidenced by [3 – 12]. There is also a respectable number of publications covering elastic [13 – 21] and viscoelastic [22 – 29] fundamental PZT concepts.

Extensive research on elastic and aeroelastic piezo control and harvesting is reported in [30 – 36].

2 ANALYSIS

2.1 General considerations

Consider a Cartesian coordinate system $x = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ with generalized displacements $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}(x, t) = \{u_1(x, t), u_2(x, t), \dots, u_{DOF}(x, t)\}$. In a dynamical flexible system that includes aerodynamic, control, mechanical damping, thermodynamic, piezoelectric, elastic and viscoelastic forces, the governing relations can be written symbolically as

$$\mathcal{L}_\ell\{\mathbf{u}(x, t)\} = \begin{cases} F(x, t) & \text{open loop} \\ \text{or} \\ F[x, t, \mathcal{L}_l^1\{\mathbf{u}\}] & \text{closed loop} \end{cases} \quad \ell \in [1 L], l \in [1 L^1] \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{L}_ℓ and \mathcal{L}_l^1 are integro-differential operators that define the integral partial differential equations (IPDE). If one includes aero-viscoelastic-servo-controllers (aero-servo-viscoelasticity), that are not treated here but in [40], and piezoelectric forces then a general expression covering all governing relations becomes symbolically (schematically) as

$$\begin{aligned} & \boxed{\text{inertia forces, } T_1} + \boxed{\text{mechanical damping forces, } T_2} + \boxed{\text{structural stiffness, } T_3} - \boxed{\text{thermal expansions, } T_4} + \boxed{\text{aero-servo-controllers, } T_5} \\ & + \boxed{\text{piezoelectric devices, including bonding agents } T_6} + \boxed{\text{flexible aerodynamic lift and drag forces and moments, } T_7} + \boxed{\text{aerodynamic property changes through morphing, } T_8} = \\ & \boxed{\text{lift and drag contributions due to rigid body motion, } T_9} + \boxed{\text{time dependent external forces independent of } u, T_{10}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

All contributions on the right of the equal sign in (2) are open loop while those on the left are closed loop ones. These concepts translate into the following governing relations

$$\mathcal{L}_\ell\{\mathbf{u}(x, t)\} = \underbrace{\sum_{m=3}^{M_c} C_m(x) \frac{\partial^m \mathbf{u}(x, t)}{\partial t^m}}_{\text{differential servo-controllers}} + [I_2(x) + A_2(x) + C_2(x)] \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}(x, t)}{\partial t^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left[S_1(x) + A_1(x)(x) + C_1(x) + \underbrace{D_1(x)}_{\substack{\text{damping} \\ \text{coefficient}}} \right] \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}(x, t)}{\partial t} \\
& + \left(\underbrace{[1 + \iota \mathbf{g}(x)] S_V^E(x, 0)}_{\substack{\text{elastic modulus and} \\ \text{structural damping}}} + A_0(x) + C_0(x) \right) \mathbf{u}(x, t) + \underbrace{\int_0^t \frac{\partial S_V(x, t, t')}{\partial t'} \mathbf{u}(x, t') dt'}_{\text{viscoelastic structural forces}} \\
& - \underbrace{\int_0^t \frac{\partial S_V^E(x, t, t')}{\partial t'} \mathbf{E}(x, t') dt'}_{\text{viscoelastic piezoelectric forces}} + \underbrace{\int_0^t \frac{\partial S_V^T(x, t, t')}{\partial t'} \mathbf{u}^T(x, t') dt'}_{\text{viscoelastic thermal expansions}} \\
& + \underbrace{C_I(x) \int_0^t \mathbf{u}(x, t') dt'}_{\substack{\text{integral servo-controllers can} \\ \text{be multiple integrals}}} = \underbrace{F(x, t)}_{\substack{\text{external forces and rigid} \\ \text{body angle of attack and} \\ \text{trim angle contributions}}} \quad \text{for } t \in [-\infty, 0] \quad \ell \in [1, L] \quad (3)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
I_2(x) &= \text{inertia terms} & F(x, t) &= \text{uncoupled forces independent of } \mathbf{u}(x, t) \\
S_n(x), S_V(x, t), S_V^T(x, t) &= \text{structural coefficients} & \mathbf{g}(x) &= \text{structural damping coefficients} \\
A_n[x, t, V(t)] &= \text{aerodynamic coefficients} & C_n(x) &= \text{aero - servo - control coefficients} \\
S(x, 0) = S_V(x, 0) + S_V^E(x, 0) + S_V^T(x, 0) &= \text{instantaneous elastic, electric, thermal moduli} & & (4)
\end{aligned}$$

The initial conditions are

$$\mathbf{u}(x, t) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad S_V(x, t) = S(x, 0) = S_E(x) \quad t \in [-\infty, 0] \quad (5)$$

where the operator S_E depends on the elastic instantaneous modulus E_0 .

The aero-piezo-servo-thermo-viscoelasticity governing relations may be summarized by rearranging Eqs. (3) so that rigid and flexible body aerodynamic forces appear on the right side

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{L}} \left\{ \mathbf{u}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t}, \dots, \frac{\partial^{\mathcal{M}} \mathbf{u}}{\partial t^{\mathcal{M}}} \right\} = \begin{cases} F_{aero} \left(\alpha_r, \mathbf{u}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t}, \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}}{\partial t^2} \right) & \text{unsteady aerodynamics} \\ & \text{(flutter, gusts, buffeting, etc.)} \\ F_{aero} \left(\alpha_r, \mathbf{u}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \right) & \text{quasi - static aerodynamics} \\ & \text{(divergence, control reversal, etc.)} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, L$ and $\mathcal{M} \in [2, \mathcal{M}_c]$

where α_r is the rigid angle of attack (aoa) defined by

$$\alpha_r(x, t) = \underbrace{\alpha(x)}_{\substack{\text{built in} \\ \text{aoa}}} - \underbrace{\alpha_0(x)}_{\substack{\text{zero lift} \\ \text{aoa}}} + \underbrace{\alpha_{trim}(t)}_{\substack{\text{flight aoa} \\ \text{trim aoa}}} + \underbrace{\alpha_{morph}(x, t)}_{\substack{\text{optional aoa} \\ \text{aoa due to} \\ \text{morphing}}} \quad (7)$$

The generalized displacements in (6) refer to plunging u_3 and chord wise u_1 bending and to torsional (twisting) u_2 motion. If chord wise bending is present in the system then the the total aoa is additionally altered by

$$\frac{\partial u_1(x, t)}{\partial x_1} \approx \arctan \left[\frac{\partial u_1(x, t)}{\partial x_1} \right] \quad (8)$$

and its partial derivatives w.r.t. time t . Generally, the trim angle will not vary chord- and/or span- wise and the other two aoa in (7) will not vary in time unless morphing is employed.

Finally, the power delivered by all the DC PZT devices is at any given time t and over a period $0 \leq t \leq t_a$

$$POW(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \mathcal{V}_k(t) \mathcal{I}_k(t) \quad \text{and} \quad POW_{total}(t_a) = \int_0^{t_a} \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \mathcal{V}_k(t') \mathcal{I}_k(t') dt' \quad (9)$$

where \mathcal{K} is the total number of PZT devices and \mathcal{V}_k and \mathcal{I}_k are the DC voltages and currents in each device k .

2.2 Solutions to governing relations

Eqs. (3) and (8) are linear integral-partial differential equations (IPDEs). If starting transients are neglected then the instantaneous appearance of a periodic solution results [47]. The homogeneous part of these IPDEs admits solutions of the type

$$\mathbf{u}(x, t) = \Re \left\{ \underbrace{[A_R(x, V, \omega) + \imath A_I(x, V, \omega)]}_{\text{amplitude} = \mathcal{A}(\imath, x, V, \omega)} \exp \left([\widehat{d}(V, \omega) + \imath \omega] t \right) \right\} \quad (10)$$

with \widehat{d} , A_R and A_I real functions of real variables.

These \mathbf{u} expressions are stable for all $t < \infty$ however when $\widehat{d} > 0$ they grow exponentially with

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \exp [\widehat{d}(V, \omega)t] \rightarrow \infty \quad (11)$$

Furthermore, it has been proved that even an infinite series (Fourier series) of these functions converge for all $t < \infty$ [44 – 46] and, therefore, that linear theory cannot produce finite critical times for column buckling and aero-viscoelasticity.

Consequently, an additional criterion must be selected such as maximum stress or deflection, failure criterion, delamination, etc., in order to determine t_{cr} , instability, or t_{ult} , the maximum lifetime of the lifting surface.

Eliminating the x dependence by applying Galerkin's method¹ and substituting Eq. (10) into the homogeneous part of (3) results in simultaneous relations of the type

$$B_{ij}(\imath, V, \omega) = 0 \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, DOF \quad (12)$$

with unknowns V and ω , which are determined from the determinant

$$D(\imath, V_{FLUT}, \omega_{FLUT}) = |B_{ij}(\imath, V_{FLUT}, \omega_{FLUT})| = 0 \quad (13)$$

yielding two simultaneous algebraic equations in the two unknowns

$$D_I(V_{FLUT}, \omega_{FLUT}) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad D_R(V_{FLUT}, \omega_{FLUT}) = 0 \quad (14)$$

These relations are similar to those involving elastic lifting surfaces but are modified by the viscoelastic integrals, which introduced different coefficients. A similar development can be presented for torsional divergence, control effectiveness, etc.

¹Or alternately by considering the equivalent solely time dependent situation of a rigid lifting surface on a viscoelastic support.

2.3 Aero-piezo-viscoelasticity formulations

These general linear small deformation viscoelastic models contain all known pertinent material property parameters and state variable functions

$$\sigma_{ij}(x, t) = \int_{-\infty}^t \left\{ E_{ijkl}(x, t-t') \frac{\partial \epsilon_{kl}(x, t')}{\partial t'} - E_{ijl}^{\mathbf{E}}(x, t-t') \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_l^{\mathbf{E}}(x, t')}{\partial t'} - E_{ij}^{\mathbf{T}}(x, t-t') \frac{\partial [\alpha \vartheta(x, t')]}{\partial t'} \right\} dt' \quad (15)$$

where σ_{ij} is the stress tensor, ϵ_{lk} the strain tensors, E_{ijkl} and $E_{ij}^{\mathbf{T}}$ the relaxation moduli, $\mathbf{E}_{ijl}^{\mathbf{E}}$ the electrical relaxation modulus or the piezoelectric stress/charge tensor, and $\alpha \vartheta$ the thermal expansions.

Secondly, following the developments the analytic developments in [8], [23], and [24] based on the experimental results of [25 – 28], these relations can be extended to piezo-viscoelastic behavior in terms of corresponding anisotropic relaxation moduli $E_{ijkl}(x, t)$ and/or creep compliances $C_{ijkl}(x, t)$ and piezoelectric parameters as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}(x, t) = & \underbrace{SW(x) \int_{-\infty}^t E_{ijkl}(x, t, t') \frac{\partial \epsilon_{kl}(x, t')}{\partial t'} dt'}_{\text{material stress-strain dependence, } \mathcal{I}_1} - \underbrace{SW_P(x) \int_{-\infty}^t E_{ijl}^{\mathbf{E}}(x, t, t') \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_l^{\mathbf{E}}(x, t')}{\partial t'} dt'}_{\text{electric potential \& permittivity contributions, } \mathcal{I}_2} \\ & + \underbrace{SW_B(x) \int_{-\infty}^t E_{ijkl}^{\mathbf{B}}(x, t, t') \frac{\partial \epsilon_{lk}(x, t')}{\partial t'} dt'}_{\text{bonding material contributions, } \mathcal{I}_3} - \underbrace{SW_T(x) \int_{-\infty}^t E_{ij}^{\mathbf{T}}(x, t, t') \frac{\partial [\alpha \vartheta(x, t')]}{\partial t'} dt'}_{\text{thermal expansion effects } \mathcal{I}_4} \\ & - \underbrace{SW_{C_1} \int_{T^*}^T \phi_{ij}^{\text{th}}(x, t, t') dt'}_{\text{temperature effects during cure, } \mathcal{I}_5} - \underbrace{SW_{C_2} \int_{\beta^*}^{\beta} \phi_{ij}^{\text{ch}}(x, t, t') dt'}_{\text{chemical effects during cure, } \mathcal{I}_6} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and

$$\underbrace{D_i(x, t')}_{\substack{\text{electric} \\ \text{displacement} \\ \text{vectors}}} = SW(x) \left[\underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t E_{ikl}^{\mathbf{E}}(x, t, t') \frac{\partial \epsilon_{kl}(x, t')}{\partial t'} dt'}_{\text{strain-displacement dependence, } \mathcal{I}_7} + \underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t E_{il}^{\mathbf{E}}(x, t, t') \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_l(x, t')}{\partial t'} dt'}_{\text{electricpotential effects, } \mathcal{I}_8} - \underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t E_i^{\mathbf{T}}(x, t, t') \frac{\partial [\alpha \vartheta(x, t')]}{\partial t'} dt'}_{\text{thermal expansion contributions, } \mathcal{I}_9} \right] \quad (17)$$

where E_{ij}^{th} are thermal anisotropic relaxation moduli, E_{ij}^{ch} are chemical shrinkage anisotropic relaxation functions and $T^*(x, t^*)$ and $\beta^*(x, t^*)$ respectively are stress-free cure reference temperatures and the corresponding degrees of cure, occurring at some initial cure time t^* . The $SW_I(\theta)$ are 3-dimensional switches with values

$$SW_I(x) = \begin{cases} H(x - x^*) & \text{action for } x \geq x^* \text{ only} \\ H(x - x^*) - H(x - x^{**}) & \text{action for } x^* \leq x \leq x^{**} \text{ only} \\ \delta(x - x^*) & \text{action at } x = x^* \text{ only} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Figure 1: PZT energy flow: control or harvesting or both?

Figure 2: Typical 1-D composite delamination experimental results [42]

delineate the spatial and/or temporal regions over which the various integrals make contributions. The individual moduli are defined by Prony series [37]

$$E_{ijkl}(x, t) = E_{ijkl}^{\infty}(x, \mathcal{F}(x)) + \sum_{n=1}^{N_{ijkl}} \underline{E}_{ijkln}[x, \mathcal{F}(x)] \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\underline{\tau}_{ijkln}[x, \mathcal{F}_1(x)]}\right) \quad (19)$$

where the underlined indices indicate no summation and the \mathcal{F} are functionally graded viscoelastic material (VFGM) functions.

2.4 Lifting surface aero-viscoelastic equilibrium and stability conditions and material failures

The principal, though not exclusive, stability conditions in aero-viscoelasticity are torsional divergence, flutter and control reversal. As previously noted criteria that are distinct from established elastic and viscoelastic ones must be defined, to wit

$$\begin{aligned} \text{torsional divergence and flutter} &\implies \begin{cases} \text{elastic :} & \lim_{V \rightarrow V_{cr}^e} u_m^e(x, V) \rightarrow \infty \\ \text{viscoelastic :} & \lim_{\substack{V \rightarrow V_{cr} \\ t \rightarrow t_{cr}}} u_m(x, t, V) \rightarrow \infty \end{cases} \\ \text{control reversal and effectiveness} &\implies \begin{cases} \text{elastic :} & \lim_{V \rightarrow V_{REV}^e} p^e(x, V, \beta) \rightarrow 0 \\ \text{viscoelastic :} & \lim_{\substack{V \rightarrow V_{REV}^e \\ t \rightarrow t_{REV}}} p(x, t, V, \beta) \rightarrow 0 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $V_{cr} = V_{DIV}$ or V_{FLUT} . The symbol p represents the rolling velocity and β is the control surface deflection angle.

Separately and independently the lifting surface material composite is subject to failures, such as delaminations of composites - see Fig. 2. Additionally, an appropriate failure criterion must be selected to define 3-D failures under combined loads [41]. These failure criteria in turn serve to establish the upper bounds of V_{max} or V_{ult} and t_{ult} , such that

$$F_{fail}(V_{max}, \sigma_{max}, t_{ult}, \text{failure properties}) = 0 \quad (21)$$

The statement of the problem at hand then is to determine the optimum combination of parameters that allows for the harvesting of the maximum amount of energy without decreasing the specified V_{DIV} , V_{FLUT} , V_{REV} , t_{DIV} , t_{FLUT} and t_{REV} or material failure conditions. Or even more advantageously the

Figure 3: Flow diagram for optimizing protocol [1], [2]

Figure 4: Viscoelastic flutter velocity and stored power

question can be posed, can the conditions be improved by delaying the critical times t_{cr} , t_{REV} and/or increasing the velocities at which instabilities occur Fig. 4 through the piezo devices while harvesting. Certainly, this has been achieved with aero-servo-viscoelastic controls without energy harvesting in [43].

3 OPTIMUM DESIGNER LIFTING SURFACE FORMULATIONS

In the present formulation there are any one or more or all of four main groups of parameters to consider simultaneously, i.e. aerodynamic, material properties, geometry (sizing) and control (servo, PZT, etc.). The detailed parameters $\mathbf{S} = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_L\}$ and their defining equations are:

Eqs. (3), governing relations, servo, inertia, sizing, aerodynamic, structural and material coefficients: $C_m, I_2, A_n, D_1, S_1, S^0, E_{ijkl}^0, E_{ijkl}^\infty$;

Eqs. (15), piezoelectric parameters: E_{ijk}^E, E^T ;

Eqs. (16), piezoelectric parameters: E_{ijk}^B ;

Eqs. (19), relaxation modulus and VFGM functions: $E_{ijkln}, \tau_{ijkln}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{F}_1$.

Additionally, there are imposed constraints consisting of prescribed parameters $\mathbf{S}^* = \{S_1^*, S_2^*, \dots, S_c^*\}$

Eq. (7), flight conditions: $(L/D)_{max}$, trim angle;

Eqs. (9), harvested power: POW_{max} ;

Eqs. (20), flutter conditions: $V_{cr}, \omega_{cr}, t_{cr}$;

Eq. (21), structural failure conditions: V_{max}, V_{ult} ;

Refs. [1], [2], operational constraints: W_{min} , dimensions, cost, mission, etc.

In the case of composites additional parameters must be included in the previous sets. These consist of number of plies, ply orientation, stacking sequences, volume fractions, delamination and cracking failures, etc.

The optimizing solution protocol is outlined in detail in [1] and [2]. The unknown parameters are the set $\mathbf{S} = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_L\}$.

A brief outline of the optimizing protocol is as follows:

Their total ensemble then forms the system of systems simultaneous relations, which can be expressed as

$$\text{governing relations} \implies \mathcal{L}(x, t, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{S}) = \{\mathcal{L}_q^p(x, t, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{S})\} = 0 \quad (22)$$

and

$$\text{constraints} \implies \mathcal{C}(x, t, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{S}^*) = \{\mathcal{C}_\ell^p(x, t, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{S}^*)\} = 0 \quad (23)$$

Eqs. (22) and (23) are the governing relations for the optimized system and their solutions for the parameter set \mathbf{S} analytically defines its many details. The \mathbf{S} parameters contain composite properties such as number of plies, orientation, fiber and matrix properties, etc.

A brief outline of the protocol to be followed is shown in Fig. 3. This inverse procedure consists of the following:

1. Derive governing relations for the problem, which in generic form are shown in (3).
2. For each system formulate desired constraints C_ℓ^p based on the prescribed specifications for the entire vehicle. However, in many cases these specifications may be derived requirements from the overall vehicle specifications in the system engineering sense.
3. Eliminate the spatial dependence of the state variables by applying Galerkin's procedure.
4. Solve the governing relations (3) for the remaining temporal functions

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{S}, t) = \int_a^b \mathbf{u}(x, t, \mathbf{S}) \mathbf{u}_m^p(x, t) dx \quad p = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{P} \quad \text{and} \quad q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{Q} \quad (24)$$

5. Eliminate the temporal dependence by least square fits or through the collocation method or by evaluation at prescribed life times t_{LF}

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{S}) = \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{S}, t_{LF}) \quad (25)$$

or other specified times. Alternately, another specification could involve a time averaging process, such that

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{S}) = \frac{1}{t_{LF}} \int_0^{t_{LF}} \hat{\mathbf{u}}(t') dt' \quad (26)$$

6. Formulate $\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{P}$ simultaneous equations of the $\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{P}$ unknown parameters through the application of Lagrange multipliers λ_ℓ such that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial S_m^p} \{ \tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{S}) + \lambda_\ell C_n^p(\mathbf{S}) \} = 0 \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{M} \quad \text{and} \quad p = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{P} \quad (27)$$

or any other proper expression(s) that one wishes to optimize. See Section 2.4 for a listing of parameters associated with the present analysis.

7. After the Lagrange multipliers λ_ℓ are eliminated in (27), one can solve the simultaneous algebraic transcendental equations for each and all S_m^p , thus realizing the optimized system of systems configuration.
8. Fig. 3 pictorially summarizes and illustrates the above protocols.

4 DISCUSSION

Typical performance figures per piezoelectric device are $E_0 \sim 1 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}$, $V = -30 \rightarrow 150$ volts and power = $2 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}$. While the output power per PZT device is small, the efficacy can be significantly augmented by distributing the devices over the entire wing span and by stacking them in order to achieve multiple outputs. The viscoelastic mechanical and electrical properties vary depending on the PZT body polymer and bonding agent.

There exists a large dichotomy in the desired results of this interactive problem. On one hand one wants large deflections in order to generate the maximum amount of power. However, from the structural failure point of view deflections should be kept at a minimum so as to not generate failures. All of these desirable conditions can be controlled through appropriate constraint relations, such as

Figure 5: PZT voltages in half-span wing with steady-state aerodynamic loads

Figure 6: Deflection and PZT energy

Eqs. (23). Aeroelastic and aero-viscoelastic stability depends on phase relations, which in linear systems are blind to deflection magnitudes.

Fig. 4 shows optimized conditions for flutter velocities and harvested energies. Note that because constraints requiring simultaneous maximum flutter velocity and maximum energy extraction occurrence at the same time were not enforced, the optimum peaks take place at different times. Consequently, the graphs represent local rather than global optimum conditions.

In Fig. 5 the spatial and temporal viscoelastic PIEZO EMF variations are displayed. As expected the best harvesting/control positions are near the wing root where the strains are the largest, cf. Eqs. (15) to (19). In Fig. 6 the evolution with ply angle of a single layer composite of maximum tip deflection and wing energy production per weight are shown.

These are single phenomena studies and over all system of system optimizations would bring all collective optimum parameters together. This global optimized state build on compromises and would not necessarily correspond to individual optimum conditions as illustrated in Figs. 4 to 6. It would in effect create a multi-dimensional space with the various parameters S_m as axes and variables. It is visualization at best is difficult but the approach developed in [48], as yet unexplored in detail for these types of problems, offers hope.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Energy harvesting by PZT devices is better suited for UAVs and MAVs because of the relative small piezoelectric output per device and more limited electric power requirements.

PZT devices introduced to harvest energy will also deliver beneficial or detrimental control actions, i.e. stabilizing or destabilizing motion, depending on the phase relations of a given closed loop configuration.

The optimum solution of the combined PZT harvesting and aero-control-viscoelastic effects may not be overly beneficial to each of these phenomena as they represent an optimal comprises of opposing requirements.

In the final analysis, even the limited optimal combined effects on only a lifting surface that often working on cross purposes must be examined on a case by case basis since analytic solutions of even the described subsystem of systems (wing) is too complex for anything but numerical solutions.

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